

Towards coordinated regional ocean climate projections

The CLIVAR/CORDEX task force on regional ocean modelling and climate projections

Angélique Melet¹, Samuel Somot², Elizabeth Drenkard³, Sheila Estrada-Allis⁴, Jason Holt⁵,
Marine Herrmann⁶, Doroteaciro Iovino⁷, H. E. Markus Meier⁸, Andrew Orr⁹, Marcus Thatcher¹⁰,
Shogo Urakawa¹¹, Xuebin Zhang¹⁰, Paula Salge¹², Josipa Milovac¹³

1. Mercator Ocean International, France
2. Météo-France, CNRS, Univ. Toulouse, CNRM, Toulouse, France
3. GFDL, USA
4. Center for Scientific Research and Higher Education of Ensenada (CICESE), Mexico
5. National Oceanography Centre, UK
6. Université de Toulouse, LEGOS (IRD, CNRS, CNES, UT3), Toulouse, France and LOTUS Laboratory, University of Science and Technology of Hanoi (USTH), Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology (VAST), Hanoi, Vietnam
7. CMCC Foundation - Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change, Bologna, Italy
8. Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research Warnemünde (IOW), Rostock, Germany
9. British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge, UK
10. CSIRO, Australia
11. Meteorological Research Institute/Japan Meteorological Agency, Japan
12. CoLAB +Atlantic, Portugal
13. Instituto de Física de Cantabria (IFCA), CSIC-Universidad de Cantabria, Santander Spain

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1 **Abstract**

2 More granular, regional-to-local ocean climate information on past, present and future marine
3 and coastal environments is needed for ocean climate research and to better support impact
4 analysis and ocean climate services for the context of societal decision making, such as
5 climate adaptation measures. Contemporary global climate models (e.g., Coupled Model
6 Intercomparison Project -CMIP-6 and 7) do not typically reach the spatial resolution required
7 for these applications. Dynamical downscaling using high-resolution ocean-only or fully
8 coupled regional climate models could help to address this issue, but there is currently no
9 coordinated framework in place. To pave the way for an internationally coordinated initiative
10 on regional ocean climate projections, a temporary joint CORDEX SAT (Science Advisory
11 Team) - CLIVAR OMDP (Climate Variability Ocean Model Development Panel) task force (TF)
12 was established in mid-2024. An inventory of existing simulations was conducted, revealing
13 that efforts have been fragmented so far but widespread, covering many regions worldwide.
14 Three-quarters of reported regional ocean models use ocean-only configurations, half have a
15 biogeochemistry component, and data are often provided at higher frequency compared to
16 CMIP. The most frequently downscaled scenarios are the very-high, middle-of-the-road and
17 low greenhouse gases emission scenarios. A survey on stakeholder needs highlighted the
18 importance of high-resolution simulations, interest in mean climate and extremes, across
19 variables and for a wide range of applications. A data request focused on requirements for
20 downscaled ocean climate projections was made to CMIP7. Finally, a proposition for an
21 updated set of reference ocean regions for regional climate assessment with relevance for the
22 next Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Assessment Report (AR7) is
23 presented. The TF has now evolved into a longer-term World Climate Research Programme
24 (WCRP) CLIVAR-CORDEX joint working group on regional ocean climate projections (JWG-

25 ROCP) whose objectives are presented, including the international coordination of regional
26 ocean climate projections and of their evaluation.

27 **1 Introduction**

28 Climate change is strongly altering the ocean with adverse effects such as rising temperature
29 and sea levels, loss of sea ice, ocean acidification, and de-oxygenation (Intergovernmental
30 Panel On Climate Change (IPCC), 2021). Ocean changes and climatic impacts drivers (CIDs,
31 i.e. physical climate system conditions that affect an element of society or ecosystems, Ruane
32 et al., 2022) can induce widespread risks and tremendous impacts worldwide, especially in
33 coastal zones (IPCC, 2022). Indeed, coastal areas have high concentration of population,
34 marine ecosystems and assets: 1 billion people currently live within 10 km of the coastline
35 (Cosby et al., 2024) and the fast-growing ocean economy, more developed in coastal zones,
36 was estimated to be worth around \$2.6 trillion in 2020 (OECD, 2025).

37 It has thus become increasingly important to align regional ocean climate information with the
38 scales of relevance to society's decision contexts at national, sub-national or more local scales,
39 to enable the design and implementation of mitigation and adaptation measures that protect
40 people, resources and the environment, including via ocean climate services (Ranasinghe et
41 al., 2021).

42 However, climate projections of the marine environment are currently mostly generated using
43 relatively coarse resolution global climate models (GCMs, e.g. from the Coupled Model
44 Intercomparison Project (CMIP) have a typical ocean resolution of 1°, Hewitt et al., 2022).
45 Despite providing invaluable knowledge on past and future changes of Earth's climate,
46 including for the ocean, information from the latest generation of GCMs (CMIP6) remains
47 insufficiently detailed to support effective decision-making in regions and localities (Fig 1). A
48 few relatively high-resolution (10-25 km in the ocean), eddy-permitting GCMs have been
49 developed (e.g., HighResMIP, Haarsma et al., 2016, Roberts et al., 2025), but most climate

50 models will not be high-resolution (i.e., $1/10^\circ$ or higher in the ocean) in CMIP7 (Hewitt et al.,
51 2022), particularly those including a representation of the marine ecosystem.

52 To provide refined regional-to-local information on ocean and CIDs past, present, and future
53 changes, GCMs can be downscaled using process-based ocean regional (limited-area)
54 climate models (ORCMs, coupled to or forced by an atmospheric model). Compared to GCMs,
55 ORCMs benefit from increased spatial resolution, more tailored model configurations for the
56 area of interest (e.g., choice of coordinates and model grid, choice and calibration of
57 parameterizations), allow a better representation of the topography and land/sea distinction
58 and more detailed process representation (e.g., sub-mesoscale processes and eddies,
59 topography-related processes, addition of components such as tides, surges or more complex
60 representation of ocean biogeochemistry) as well as the possibility to select and bias-correct
61 forcings from GCMs.

62

63

64 *Figure 1. From global climate models to regional ocean climate models. The schematic illustrates the refinement of*
65 *model meshes, the increased complexity of regional models (variables, components) and several climate risks and*
66 *blue economy markets. Credit: Mercator Ocean International.*

67 Ocean climate downscaling is a dynamic research area and has developed for different regions
68 around the world (e.g., reviews in Drenkard et al., 2021 and Holt et al., 2025). However, such
69 initiatives lack international coordination and so far have been highly fragmented, primarily
70 focused on research purposes or specific regional applications, with each group using a
71 different approach for scenario and CMIP model selections, experimental design, applications
72 and validation. In contrast, regional atmospheric climate projections are coordinated through
73 the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX, Gutowski et al., 2016),
74 endorsed by the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) Regional Information for
75 Society (RIfS) core project. CORDEX's vision is to advance and coordinate the science and
76 application of regional climate downscaling through global partnerships. CORDEX also
77 evaluates the added value of regional downscaling. However, CORDEX has mostly focused
78 so far on the atmosphere and land, with only a few CORDEX regions including ocean models
79 (e.g., Ruti et al., 2016 for Med-CORDEX).

80 To address this gap, a joint CORDEX SAT (Science Advisory Team) - CLIVAR OMDP (Climate
81 Variability Ocean Model Development Panel) task force (TF) has been established to develop
82 a strategic plan for a long-term initiative on regional ocean climate projections within the WCRP
83 (Section 2). To inform its strategic planning and prepare future actions, the TF carried out
84 various activities, such as contributing to characterizing stakeholder needs, surveying existing
85 simulations on regional ocean climate projections, identifying existing coordinating
86 frameworks, and initiatives and requirements for future coordinated protocols, submitting a
87 data request for CMIP7 and proposing a revised set of ocean reference regions for regional
88 ocean climate assessments. This TF paved the way for the creation in 2026 of a new, longer
89 term WCRP CLIVAR-CORDEX joint working group on regional ocean climate projections
90 (JWG ROCP), which notably aims at international coordination of regional ocean climate
91 projections (Section 3). Conclusions are provided in Section 4.

92 **2 Paving the way for a coordinating initiative for regional** 93 **ocean climate projections**

94 Regional ocean climate projections have been identified by CORDEX as one of their
95 community challenges requiring rapid coordination and strategic planning, as well as
96 collaboration with other WCRP and external communities. CORDEX's SAT decided to
97 implement a new instrument (Task Force, TF) for short-term planning actions to address rapidly
98 evolving challenges in coordination with other relevant initiatives, where appropriate. The
99 primary goal of a TF is to identify strategic needs and tasks, ultimately developing a proposal
100 of planning steps to implement these activities within the CORDEX framework.

101 At the same time, in CLIVAR, OMDP expanded its activities towards regional ocean climate
102 modelling and projections. A joint CLIVAR-OMDP and CORDEX-SAT TF on "Regional ocean
103 modelling and climate projections" was thus established during Summer 2024 for a year and
104 a half (Annex 1).

105 To inform its strategic planning and prepare future actions, the TF carried out different activities
106 such as identifying stakeholder needs (Section 2.1), surveying existing simulations on regional
107 ocean climate projections (Section 2.2), identifying existing coordinating frameworks and
108 initiatives and requirements for future coordinated protocols (Section 2.3), submitting a data
109 request for CMIP7 (Section 2.4) and proposing a revised set of ocean reference regions for
110 regional ocean climate assessments (Section 2.5).

111 **2.1. Making regional ocean climate projections data actionable: Engaging with** 112 **stakeholders**

113 For regional ocean climate data to be more actionable, engaging with stakeholders to
114 understand their needs is essential. A stakeholder survey was conducted in the framework of
115 the Horizon Europe SEACLIM project (Melet et al., 2025) to collect information on how regional

116 ocean climate information is perceived and applied in practice (Salge et al., 2026). 790
 117 responses were collected from users distributed across all major ocean basins, from different
 118 communities (Fig 2, from academic and research institutions (64%), private companies (16%),
 119 government agencies (13%), and non-governmental organizations (4%)) and with different
 120 profiles (including both intermediate and end-users, with half of them using ocean climate
 121 projections, and a third of them planning to). The survey therefore provides a broad, although
 122 not fully representative, snapshot of current user expectations regarding regional ocean
 123 climate information. Regarding sectorial applications, scientific research, long-term risk
 124 assessment, climate adaptation planning and marine ecosystem modelling - habitat
 125 projections were the four most frequently selected ones.
 126

127
 128 *Figure 2. Illustrative results of the SEACLIM stakeholder survey on needs for regional ocean decadal predictions*
 129 *and climate projections. Panel (C) focuses exclusively on climate projections.*

130 Results showed a convergence across sectors on the need for high-resolution ocean
 131 information (1-to-10 km resolution, compared to 10-25 km and coarser than 25 km resolutions,

132 Fig 2). The most requested ocean variables (by >75% of respondents) are: sea surface
133 temperature and salinity, sea level and surface ocean currents for ocean physics, sea-ice
134 concentration, thickness and extent for sea-ice, significant wave height, mean wave direction
135 and period, and the height and period of wind-sea waves. However, ocean biogeochemistry
136 variables were also requested, such as surface phytoplankton concentration, dissolved oxygen
137 concentration, pH, primary production, 3D phytoplankton and zooplankton concentrations, and
138 nitrate and phosphate concentrations. Stakeholders expressed consistent interest in variables
139 across multiple temporal scales, from 20-yr mean changes to seasonal and interannual
140 variability and extreme events. In terms of variable frequencies, daily and monthly means are
141 the most requested ones, except for wind-waves and surface physical ocean variables for
142 which hourly data were also largely requested. Regarding time horizons of interest, both mid-
143 century (2050) and end-century (2100) projections were requested, although it should be noted
144 that interest in decadal predictions (1-to-10-yr outlook) was also clearly expressed. There could
145 also be need for longer-term horizons (e.g., 2150, 2300), but these were not characterized by
146 this survey. In terms of shared-socioeconomic scenarios (SSPs), respondents mostly use the
147 fossil fueled development world/very-high emission SSP5-8.5 (61%), followed by the middle-
148 of-the-road SSP2-4.5 (55%), the sustainability/low emission SSP1-2.6 (45%), with the high
149 emission SSP3-7.0 being used by 34% of the respondents. These stakeholder needs should
150 inform the prioritization of coordinated protocols, but they must be balanced against modelling
151 feasibility, regional process relevance, and data volume constraints.

152

153 Participants also expressed their expectations regarding data quality and uncertainty
154 communication. The majority emphasized the importance of validation of historical simulations
155 against observations or other reference datasets (e.g., reanalysis) as well as the validation of
156 reference simulations forced by reanalysis data – often called “evaluation runs” or “hindcasts”.

157 Regarding uncertainty, users expressed a preference for standard metrics and IPCC-style
158 terminology, supported by visual representations such as confidence ranges, accompanied by
159 clear descriptions of sources of uncertainty. These findings highlight the need for ongoing
160 dialogue between data producers, modelers and end-users to translate coherent regional
161 ocean climate projections into actionable products that can be used directly by climate
162 research, services and adaptation planning as well as management.

163

164 **2.2. An inventory of existing regional ocean climate projections**

165 To identify the extent to which regional ocean climate projections have been performed by
166 different groups worldwide, the TF surveyed the ocean modeling community to aid in compiling
167 an inventory of existing regional ocean climate change projections simulations. The survey
168 (Drenkard et al., 2026) queries and collects information regarding model configurations such
169 as the regional focus and geographic extent, details regarding spatial resolution (e.g.,
170 horizontal grid spacing and number/type of vertical layers), and model components (i.e.,
171 underlying ocean physics, biogeochemistry, and sea ice models). We received 76 applicable
172 responses by the cutoff date of end 2025 (summarized in Annex 2), with domain sizes ranging
173 from regional bays to entire ocean basins (Fig 3). The survey results showed that, in most
174 cases, ocean model grids cover limited areas, though a subset of configurations (6.6%) consist
175 of global grids with a higher horizontal resolution in the region of interest (i.e., adaptive mesh
176 refinement). With regards to model components, all studies included an ocean physics model
177 (Fig 3A), 47.4% of studies simulated ocean biogeochemistry (Fig 3B), while 31.6% included
178 sea ice (Fig 3C). While inclusion of a sea ice module may not be relevant for lower latitude,
179 limited area configurations, we did include global configurations with high resolution focus at
180 low latitudes in the sea ice count in Figure 3C (1 survey response). The rationale is that a sea
181 ice module was part of the model architecture and while sea ice itself may be unlikely to occur

182 in the region of interest, the effects of sea ice as remote processes are included. Note that the
183 survey focuses only on compiling the projection simulations, and not evaluation runs.
184

185

186 *Figure 3. Approximate geographic extents of ocean model configurations used to downscale climate projections*
 187 *that were submitted to the task force inventory survey. The panels are organized by inclusion of model components*
 188 *of (A) ocean physics, (B) ocean biogeochemistry (BGC), and (C) sea ice.*

189
 190 *Figure 4. Number of CMIP5 and CMIP6 emission scenarios downscaled to produce regional ocean climate*
 191 *projections (A) and the highest temporal frequency of selected key model outputs (B) reported through the TF*
 192 *inventory survey. The model outputs shown are for surface variables: sea surface height (ssh), surface temperature*
 193 *(tos), surface salinity (sos), surface velocity (uos, vos), surface chlorophyll (chlos); for 3D variables: potential*
 194 *temperature (thetao), salinity (so), velocity (uo, vo), dissolved oxygen (o2), nitrate (no3), phosphate (po4), iron (dfe)*
 195 *concentrations; and 2D variables including primary production (pp), mixed layer depth (mld), sea ice concentration*
 196 *(sic).*

197 While 75% of survey responses reported configurations utilizing ocean-only configurations with
 198 one-way atmospheric forcings, 25% implemented coupled ocean-atmosphere configurations.
 199 The distribution of downscaled forcing scenarios is reported in Figure 4A. Emphasis so far has
 200 clearly been on the higher end of emission scenarios (i.e., SSP5-8.5 and RCP8.5). However,
 201 there does appear to be a shift towards a more evenly distributed representation of lower
 202 emission scenarios from CMIP6 scenarios (i.e., SSP1-2.6 to SSP3-7.0) relative to CMIP5
 203 scenarios (i.e., RCP2.6 to RCP6.0). It could be noted here that CMIP7 scenarios cover a

204 narrower range of greenhouse gases emission compared to CMIP6 (Van Vuuren et al., 2026a),
205 due to a revised plausibility of very low and high emission scenarios. The very-high emission
206 of SSP5-8.5 has become implausible, based on trends in the costs of renewables, the
207 emergence of climate policy and recent emission trends (Hausfather and Peters, 2020; United
208 Nations Environment Programme, 2025; e.g., Van Vuuren et al., 2026a). Additional
209 downscaled forcing scenarios were also reported: 1.5xCO₂ (1 response), 2xCO₂ (2
210 responses), 4xCO₂ (1 response), and SRES-A1B (2 responses).

211 We also asked survey participants to provide information regarding model output, including the
212 temporal frequency of a subset of key output variables (Fig 4B), and whether model output
213 was available/accessible to external users.

214 High frequency (i.e., daily or hourly) output was more common for 2D and ocean physics
215 variables, which is to be expected given large file sizes of 3D variables, and that fewer than
216 half of the configurations represent ocean biogeochemistry, which contributes to reduced
217 biogeochemistry output at all temporal frequencies (Fig 3B). Model output availability varied -
218 while some responses cited output that was publicly available on existing platforms, many
219 indicated that output was shareable upon request. About half of survey responses reported
220 that their simulations were part of a coordinated effort (e.g., Med-CORDEX, projects and
221 programmes, and direct collaboration with other institute(s)).

222 The simulation inventory is an ongoing effort and is not exhaustive, as it relies on the
223 community's completion of the survey. Current inventory results are Europe-centric in terms of
224 domain coverage (Fig 3), and continued efforts to distribute the survey will likely show an
225 increase in coverage diversity. Additionally, we plan to make the survey results publicly
226 available (with respondent permission) as a resource for future downscaling modeling studies
227 and initiatives. This survey will also inform recommendations regarding community needs and
228 priorities.

229

230 **2.3. Existing and requirements for coordinating frameworks and initiatives**

231 Coordinated modelling and evaluation protocols are needed for:

- 232 • Developing multi-model simulation experiments for projections and quantification of
233 uncertainties
- 234 • Performing multi-model intercomparisons (e.g., including choice of common metrics,
235 reference datasets, time periods)
- 236 • Providing standardized outputs to the community (data request, archiving
237 specifications) allowing to easily handle multi-model studies a posteriori
- 238 • Assessing the added-value & fitness-for-purpose of regionally downscaled projections

239 Besides, defining a coordinated experimental protocol is key to foster discussions, mutual
240 understanding and joint initiatives within the regional ocean modelling community. Following
241 coordinated protocols ensures consistency in the modelling framework and facilitates more
242 robust multi-model assessments. Since model uncertainty is one of the major sources of
243 uncertainty in climate projections (Hawkins and Sutton, 2009; Evin et al., 2021), following a
244 common experimental protocol and developing multi-model simulations enables this
245 contribution to be quantified.

246 **2.3.1. Existing coordinated protocols**

247 Diverse community-built protocols for ocean simulations, validation and data requests have
248 been developed for climate projections such as (i) WCRP CMIP ScenarioMIP (O'Neill et al.,
249 2016; Van Vuuren et al., 2026; Dunne et al., 2025; Fox-Kemper et al., 2025) and ESMValTool
250 (Eyring et al., 2020), (ii) decadal predictions (Boer et al., 2016), (iii) atmospheric downscaling
251 (Gutowski et al., 2016; Solman et al., 2021; CORDEX (2025) for the CORDEX-CMIP6
252 experiment design, Nikulin et al., 2025 for the CORDEX-CMIP6 archiving specifications), (iv)

253 fully-coupled regional downscaling (Somot et al., 2024; Sevault and Somot, 2024 for Med-
254 CORDEX-CMIP6 simulation protocol and ocean data request), (v) global ocean modelling
255 (e.g., OMIP: Griffies et al., 2016; Tsujino et al., 2020; operational oceanography: e.g., Le Traon
256 et al., 2019 and its Product Quality Strategy, Copernicus Marine Service, 2021). However,
257 these protocols and best practices need to be adapted to deliver community-coordinated
258 regional ocean climate modelling experiments and their validation (Section 3.2.1), to foster the
259 development of quality-assessed regional ocean model ensembles and intercomparisons. To
260 the best of our knowledge, there is no coordinated experimental protocol for regional ocean
261 climate projections with worldwide applications.

262 **2.3.2. Requirements for coordinated protocols**

263 From the authors' past experiences, defining RCM protocols is often more difficult than for
264 global models as the definition of domains and more external forcings must be specified and
265 therefore agreed upon by the modelling participants. To define a common protocol for a
266 regional ocean climate projections coordinated initiative (Section 3), various choices should be
267 made, considering the diversity of the regional ocean regions. This includes at least (1) the
268 driving RCM and the minimal content of the model configurations (including coupling with other
269 components of the regional climate system) also called level of complexity, (2) the minimal
270 domain to be covered, (3) the minimal spatial and temporal resolution of the models, (4) the
271 socio-economic and climate change driving scenario(s), (5) the driving GCMs and/or RCMs,
272 ensemble mean vs individual members, (6) the list of the other mandatory forcings (river, lateral
273 ocean boundary conditions, aerosol-informed radiation, chlorophyll, etc.), (7) the choice of the
274 running time period, (8) the minimal ensemble size, (9) the initialization and spin-up strategy,
275 (10) the acceptance or not of a priori bias-corrections or nudging techniques as well as (11)
276 the archive specification (file format, metadata, data request).

277 In addition, a protocol for regional ocean climate projections will have to align with other
278 existing protocols such as CMIP ScenarioMIP, CORDEX or FishMIP to ensure the availability
279 of forcings for regional ocean climate simulations and to provide the expected outputs to the
280 whole climate modelling chain from scenario to impacts and adaptation. Links to the
281 Coordinated Ocean Wave Climate Project (COWCLIP, Morim et al. 2020(Morim et al., 2020))
282 protocols could also be made, as regional wave simulations could be run together or coupled
283 to ocean physics, sea-ice and biogeochemical simulations (e.g., using ocean currents and sea
284 level, Chaigneau et al., 2023) to get a complete set of regional ocean climate projections
285 covering the different ocean components. Designing an experimental protocol that is agreed
286 upon by the regional ocean climate projections community will take time, probably various
287 generations of runs, and will require flexibility to maximize uptake, that can be translated by
288 wording such as “mandatory”, “strongly recommended”, “recommended”, “welcome”
289 throughout the protocol text.

290 In coordinated protocols such as CORDEX, an evaluation run is produced to provide the “best”
291 regional ocean model simulation of the present-day as a free run (without data assimilation),
292 using forcings derived from observations and reanalysis products. It is used to evaluate the
293 quality of the regional model compared to observations as largely requested by users (Section
294 2.1), including specific events due to phased internal variability. The evaluation run can also
295 serve as a reference to evaluate historical regional ocean climate simulations using GCMs and
296 /or RCMs historical runs as forcings.

297 A coordinated evaluation framework is needed for a robust multi-model assessment and
298 evaluation. It includes the choice of a common set of metrics with a common calculation, time
299 period, reference datasets (observations, reanalyses, hindcast). As for the experimental
300 protocol, a targeted evaluation protocol for regional ocean climate projections will need to be

301 developed to complement existing ones (e.g., CMIP ESMValTool, Rapid Evaluation
302 Framework, CMEMS product quality strategy).

303 Beyond the multi-model assessment, a coordinated evaluation protocol will allow the
304 assessment of the added-value and fitness-for-purpose of regionally downscaled projections
305 in a common way across modelling centers, ensuring more robust overall conclusions (Section
306 3).

307 **2.4. Coordinated data requests**

308 Being area-limited, ORCMs need external forcings at their open boundaries, but also from
309 rivers and runoff and at their air-sea interface when used in forced mode. These forcings mostly
310 come from CMIP or regionalised CMIP models. However, some variables needed for ocean
311 downscaling (physics, biogeochemistry, sea-ice) were not included in the CMIP6 Data
312 Request. In other cases, variables were provided, but not at a sufficiently high temporal
313 resolution (e.g., to model storm surges). A Data Request was thus formulated by the TF for
314 CMIP7 DECK (pi-control and historical) and ScenarioMIP simulations, under the umbrella of
315 CORDEX (see requested variables and their frequency in Annex 3).

316 CORDEX data can also be used by ORCMs (e.g., for air-sea forcings for ocean-only models).
317 A Data Request should thus be formulated for CORDEX-CMIP7 (Fernandez et al., this issue),
318 which has not started yet, aligned with the CMIP7 Data Request.

319

320 **2.5. A proposition for revised reference ocean regions for multi-model** 321 **assessments**

322 **2.5.1. Evolution of reference ocean regions in IPCC assessment reports and caveats for** 323 **ocean regions**

324 The set of reference regions used for regional syntheses of climate information, such as used
325 in the AR6 Regional Atlas (Gutierrez et al., 2021) was refined over IPCC cycles (Fig 5A-D). In
326 IPCC AR3 and AR4, 23 rectangular regions were used (Fig 5A, Christensen et al., 2007; Giorgi
327 et al., 2001). These so-called “Giorgi regions” were refined into 26 more flexible polygons (Fig
328 5B) for the IPCC Special Report on Managing the Risks of Extreme Events and Disasters to
329 Advance Climate Adaptation (SREX, Seneviratne et al., 2012). For AR5, SREX polygons were
330 slightly modified and some regions added (island states, Arctic, Antarctica) to improve the
331 climate coherency over subcontinental scale regions, while ensuring that enough grid points
332 are included in the regions for robustness of region-averaged climate information. 33 reference
333 regions were used in AR5 (van Oldenborgh et al., 2013) including 15 ocean regions (Fig 5C).
334 However, except for the Arctic Ocean and Antarctic region, AR5 ocean regions were part of
335 land regions (only sub-domains of the Indian and tropical Pacific Ocean were designated as
336 reference regions). The rest of the main oceanic regions were not represented.

337 In AR6, thanks to a larger number of climate models and increased spatial resolution of their
338 atmospheric components, reference regions were revised mostly by splitting previous land
339 regions to increase climatic homogeneity within the region, while still ensuring
340 representativeness of the model results. AR6 reference regions included 15 ocean-only
341 regions and 47 land regions (Fig 5D). All major open ocean regions were thus included with
342 the Pacific, Atlantic and Indian Oceans being divided into equatorial, south and north regions.
343 Coastal ocean regions were included as an extension of the land regions (with a land/sea mask
344 to separate them), which were defined in terms of climatic homogeneity of mean temperature

345 and precipitation over land (considering Köppen-Geiger climatic regions, Iturbide et al., 2020).
346 This means that AR6 ocean coastal regions were not defined for the synthesis of regional
347 ocean climate information per se, but rather to be suitable for the analysis of large-scale
348 atmospheric data. This results in several caveats for regional ocean climate assessment,
349 especially for the coastal ocean and regional seas. Coastal zones were not addressed
350 consistently over the world's ocean, showing clear inhomogeneity in the coastal zone
351 extension (e.g., compare EAS and SAS in AR6, Fig 5D). Indeed, no specific criterion was used
352 to define the ocean coastal extension of land regions in the ocean (and hence, coastal ocean
353 regions). Rather, the coastal extension of land polygons in the ocean is mostly related to the
354 geometry of the shoreline, encompassing all land in the region while keeping polygons as
355 simple as possible (e.g., RAR, EAS, NAU, Fig 5D). In addition, with the land climate
356 homogeneity driving the definition of regions, some land / coastal regions encompass ocean
357 coastal zones from different ocean basins in a single region (SCA, NCA, Fig 5D). On the other
358 hand, coastal ocean regions with homogeneous climate characteristics are split into different
359 regions. For instance, the coastal zones in the Gulf of Mexico are distributed over five regions.
360 In Europe, the Bay of Biscay (north-eastern Atlantic) is also split into three regions, following
361 the split in main regional land climates in Europe. The Mediterranean Sea was a region in itself
362 but included large parts of the Black Sea. Three regions (CAR, MED, SEA, Fig 5D) were
363 considered as being both land and ocean regions (defined using the land and sea masks,
364 respectively) and did not have coastal zones.

365

366 *Figure 5. Set of reference regions used in (A) AR3 and AR4 (Giorgi regions), (B) SREX, (C) AR5 and (D) AR6. (E)*

367 *Proposition of new reference regions for the ocean for the IPCC.*

368 **2.5.2. Proposition of a revised set of open ocean, coastal and regional seas reference**
369 **regions**

370 Guidelines for the proposed updated ocean regions are based on the same basic principles
371 followed in previous initiatives for the IPCC (e.g., Iturbide et al., 2020). For the coastal ocean
372 and regional seas, which are introduced as a new element in this proposal, our proposition is
373 guided by large marine ecosystems (LMEs). LMEs are described as 66 regional units for the
374 conservation and management of living marine resources in accordance with the legal
375 mandates of the United Nations Convention for the Law Of the Sea (UNCLOS) (Sherman,
376 2015). LMEs are characterized by distinct bathymetry, hydrography (currents, water masses),
377 productivity, and food web interactions, hence ensuring ocean climate and marine ecosystems
378 considerations in defining them. LMEs encompass coastal areas to the seaward boundaries
379 of continental shelves and the outer margins of the major ocean current systems. It should be
380 noted however that some dynamical features may not be fully captured by the LME extent,
381 which could have implications for interpreting regional processes (e.g., the Loop Current linking
382 the Caribbean and the Gulf of Mexico through the Yucatan Channel). The seaward extensions
383 of LMEs tend to match these of exclusive economic zones (EEZ, defined by the UNCLOS and
384 generally extend 200 nautical miles (370 km) from shore, Fig 6). This also ensures a more
385 coherent criteria for the coastal extension of ocean regions. The size of LMEs is on the order
386 of 200,000 km² or greater, thereby ensuring the representativeness of model results with
387 enough grid cells in each LME.

388 Since 1997, the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) has promoted the LME
389 approach from a scientific point of view as well as in regions for the assessment and
390 management of marine resources. LMEs are often overfished, polluted, and encompass key
391 marine habitats facing diverse stresses (e.g., coral reefs, mangroves, seagrasses, Fig 6,
392 Sherman, 2015). Moreover, about 80% of global annual marine fishery biomass extraction

393 occurs in LMEs, which generally exhibit higher productivity in their enclosed areas than
394 adjacent open ocean productivity. In addition, LME zones contribute around 28 trillion dollars
395 annually in ecosystem services to the global economy (Sherman and Donnelly, 2026;
396 Kubiszewski et al., 2017). LMEs are thus relevant for ocean biodiversity, ocean risks and
397 economy and for the 3 IPCC Working Groups. In AR6, LMEs and / or EEZ were used in regional
398 chapters of the WG2 report.

399 LMEs were used to guide the proposition for revised reference regions for coastal ocean and
400 regional seas, but keeping the principle of simple polygons large enough for a robust
401 aggregation of regional information. LMEs guided the revision of coastal ocean regions
402 extension (e.g., in Africa, America), the addition of regional seas, gulfs and semi-enclosed
403 basins (Fig 6, Fig 5E, Annex 4).

404 Finally, only one LME exists for the coastal Antarctic. Based on discussions with CLIVAR
405 regional panels, we propose adding the Ross, Amundsen-Bellinghousen and Weddell seas as
406 well as a coastal region for East Antarctica (ORO, OAB, OWE, OEAN, Fig 5E, Fig 6, Annex 4).

407
408 For the open ocean regions, a revision was proposed by Milovac et al. (2024) based on a
409 scaling of sea surface temperature and sea surface air temperature with global warming levels.
410 Their analysis revealed potential inhomogeneities and pronounced gradients within some
411 IPCC AR6 reference regions, suggesting that boundaries of several ocean regions needed to
412 be adjusted to better capture local characteristics specific to each area. The proposed
413 adjustments include a split of the north Atlantic and Pacific oceans, South Atlantic Ocean and
414 Southern Ocean, and the addition of the Arabian Sea (Fig 7). They better fit with AR6 ocean
415 biomes (regions of the Earth generally defined by the type of fauna and flora that they support
416 in response to climatic conditions, Fay and McKinley, 2014; Gregor et al., 2019) and do not
417 affect coastal regions. We propose adopting these revisions in open ocean regions, except for

418 the separation of the South Ocean and for the addition of the Arabian Sea, following changes
419 implemented for coastal and marginal seas, to avoid too narrow Southern Ocean regions and
420 since new regions were added related to the Arabian Sea (OARS, OSCC in Fig 5E, Fig 6,
421 Annex 4). In addition, a region was added for the Tasman Sea (OTAS) as this region presents
422 a hotspot of surface ocean warming (Bulgin et al., 2020), and the equatorial Pacific was split
423 in two regions of different latitudinal range to better represent the Warm Pool and Equatorial
424 Upwelling regions, their different ocean climate conditions and marine ecosystems (e.g., Lee
425 et al., 2022).

426 The proposition of revised IPCC ocean reference regions was sent to different panels and
427 programmes to collect feedback. We received feedback from CLIVAR regional panels,
428 CORDEX domains and FPS, CMIP core panel, and from COWCLIP. Most of the feedback has
429 been accounted for. The final proposition is presented in Fig 5E; it comprises 65 ocean regions,
430 listed in Annex 4, including 15 open ocean ones, 30 regional seas, 20 coastal ocean ones
431 (compared to 56 ocean regions in AR6, with 15 open ocean ones and 41 coastal ones,
432 shapefile in Melet et al., (2026)). It should be noted, however, that LMEs do not cover small
433 island regions, and a different revision would be needed for such ocean regions.

434

435 Figure 6. Proposed revision of reference ocean regions for the IPCC (black lines) with large marine ecosystems

436 (color shading), exclusive economic zones (colored contours) and UNEP-WCMC (2025) Ocean+ Habitats: warm-

437 water corals (red dots), cold-water corals (dark cyan dots), mangroves (brown dots), seagrasses (green dots).

438

439 Figure 7. Revised open ocean regions proposed by Milovac et al. (2024) (changes compared to AR6 are shown in

440 red) and AR6 ocean biomes (grey contours). Note that the proposed split of the Southern Ocean in NSO and SSO

441 nor the split of the Indian Ocean were not adopted in the proposition of new ocean reference regions following

442 changes in coastal ocean regions and regional seas and feedback from the community.

443

444 **3 A coordinating initiative on regional ocean climate** 445 **projections**

446 Based on the information gathered by the TF and on its preparatory activities (section 2), the
447 regional ocean climate projections community appears sufficiently mature to develop and carry
448 out a worldwide and long-term coordinated initiative. In its synthesis report (Somot et al., 2025),
449 the TF thus proposed to CLIVAR OMDP and CORDEX SAT the creation of a longer-term Joint
450 Working Group on Regional Ocean Climate Projections (JWG-ROCP) with the following
451 objectives:

- 452 • **Coordinate regional ocean climate projections** (physics including sea level,
453 biogeochemistry, sea-ice, waves) worldwide by developing coordinated simulation
454 protocols for both ocean-only and coupled RCMs, and by delivering standardized
455 datasets and by supporting WCRP initiative on sea level rise and extremes (e.g., upcoming
456 WCRP Sea level Rise – Projections, Impacts & Adaptation Task Team)
- 457 • **Explore the potential of data-driven machine-learning approaches** to simulate oceanic
458 regions and their future evolution, strengthening the promising training opportunities given
459 by datasets produced with process-based numerical models
- 460 • **Advance the science of regional ocean climate modelling and projections** through
461 multi-model assessments, identification of robust biases and underlying processes
- 462 • **Engage the community of regional ocean modelers and model users** to provide a
463 forum for sharing knowledge and experience across domains
- 464 • **Serve the climate impact and adaptation needs** by engaging with relevant users and
465 stakeholders, and by providing data and expertise to ocean climate services

- 466 • **Contribute to expert assessment reports** (e.g., IPCC-AR7, national or regional
467 assessment reports)

468 Rooting the JWG in CLIVAR OMDP and CORDEX SAT is supported by:

- 469 • CLIVAR-OMDP's provision of long-term knowledge on ocean model development,
470 including tuning, spinup and parameterization development, on climate variability and
471 change over the ocean and on air-sea interactions,
- 472 • CORDEX-SAT's provision of long-term experience in worldwide coordination of regional
473 climate modelling, its capacity to produce coordinated climate projection datasets and its
474 strong connection with stakeholders, climate services and, more generally, regional climate
475 data users for the benefit of society.

476 The JWG-ROCP will be implemented in a 2-step plan. A transition phase will take place in
477 2026 during which TF members will support the JWG fast-track actions. This includes initiating
478 a first homogenization of existing simulations (section 2.2) to meet the IPCC-AR7 deadlines,
479 as well as preparing a call for nomination for new members to be appointed. From 2027
480 onwards, the JWG-ROCP will enter a longer-term implementation plan to reach a mature
481 stage. This phase will target the ocean downscaling of CMIP7 models through coordinated
482 protocols, multi-model assessment studies, and a wider contribution to future regional
483 assessment reports on climate change and the ocean (e.g., IPCC-AR8). Beyond the members
484 of the JWG, a larger community of interest will be engaged, open to members of the regional
485 ocean modelling community and the ocean climate projections users. The JWG-ROCP was
486 approved by CLIVAR OMDP, CLIVAR Scientific Steering Group (SSG) and CORDEX SAT.

487 **4 Conclusions**

488 Refined, more granular regional-to-local information is increasingly needed on the past,
489 present and future marine and coastal climate conditions for a wide range of applications,

490 including scientific research, long-term risk assessment, climate adaptation and mitigation. A
491 stakeholder survey highlights the need for information on the different marine environmental
492 components (physics, waves, biogeochemistry, sea ice) at resolution of O(10 km).

493 Dynamical downscaling leveraging on regionally tailored ocean models can bridge the gap
494 between stakeholder needs at regional scale and coarse GCMs by enabling finer resolution,
495 specific regional tuning, the representation of more processes to better address ocean climatic
496 impact drivers (e.g., explicit tides, storm surges and waves for sea level extremes), and
497 correcting forcings biases. Regional ocean climate dynamical downscaling is a growing
498 research area.

499 To address this community challenge and to identify strategic needs and tasks for a longer-
500 term initiative, a joint CLIVAR-CORDEX TF on regional ocean modelling and climate
501 projections was established from Summer 2024 to December 2025. To inform its strategic
502 planning and prepare future actions, the TF contributed to identifying stakeholder needs,
503 surveyed existing simulations on regional ocean climate projections, identified existing
504 coordinating frameworks and initiatives and requirements for future coordinated protocols,
505 submitted a data request for CMIP7 models for ocean dynamical downscaling, and proposed
506 a revised set of ocean reference regions for regional ocean climate assessments such as IPCC
507 7th assessment report. The inventory of existing regional ocean climate projections based on
508 regional ocean models (coupled or un-coupled) downscaling CMIP5 or CMIP6 GCMs shows
509 that efforts have emerged in multiple regions worldwide, resulting in an increasingly broad
510 geographical coverage. Overall, existing simulations offer a promising starting point for a first
511 homogenization of key variables and climate change scenarios, which would be a cornerstone
512 to start multi-model assessments of past and future regional ocean changes. However, ocean
513 climate dynamical downscaling efforts remain highly fragmented, and international
514 coordination is lacking. It is also worth noting the strong regional disparity in the level of

515 advancement of ocean projections (Holt et al 2025), which is linked to differences in scientific,
516 numerical, financial, and human resources and expertise, but also to the specificities of study
517 areas (for example, implementing ocean projections over the South East Asia SEA, Fig 4- is
518 very challenging due to the region's complex topography and processes, Xue et al., 2020;
519 Garinet et al., 2024).

520 The regional ocean climate projections community has reached enough maturity to initiate and
521 carry out a coordinated international and long-term framework. Therefore, the TF proposed to
522 create a longer-term Joint Working Group on Regional Ocean Climate Projections (JWG-
523 ROCP) within WCRP under the umbrella of CLIVAR OMDP and CORDEX SAT to coordinate
524 CMIP7 GCMs downscaled ocean climate projections (physics incl. sea level and wind-waves,
525 biogeochemistry, sea-ice) worldwide. The JWG-ROCP will aim at developing coordinated
526 simulation protocols for both ocean-only and coupled RCMs, addressing the experiment
527 design, evaluation framework, data request, archive specification, and standardized data
528 delivery strategy, in close collaboration with the new CORDEX Task Teams on Protocol and
529 Infrastructure (Fernandez et al., this issue) and on Machine Learning (Gutierrez et al., this
530 issue). This initiative also aims to advance the science of regional ocean climate projections
531 by linking to a large scientific community working on this topic to share knowledge and
532 experience across domains and by facilitating new scientific knowledge production (e.g.,
533 scientific challenge identification, dedicated model developments, multi-model assessments,
534 identification of robust biases and underlying processes, and exploring impact of coupling) to
535 inform the next generation of regional ocean models for climate projections. This will contribute
536 to harmonizing the level of advancement of ocean climate projections, helping to identify and
537 remove the barriers that currently prevent such projections from being implemented in certain
538 regions.

539 For the delivered datasets to be actionable and to better serve the climate impact and
540 adaptation needs, the JWG-ROCP will engage further with relevant users/stakeholders (e.g.,
541 through survey and co-design for meeting user needs) and aims to provide user-friendly data
542 and expertise to ocean climate services (e.g., through model documentation, errata services,
543 user guidelines, user-friendly data access for user experience).

544 Although this longer-term initiative would be rooted in the CLIVAR and CORDEX communities,
545 links with other WCRP panels and programmes and international initiatives (e.g., COWCLIP
546 for wind-waves, Digital Twins, RfS, and UN Ocean Decade programmes such as CoastPredict
547 and Foresea) would be developed.

548

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846 **Annex 1. Task force description and members**

847 The **Regional ocean modelling and climate projections task force** is a joint initiative from
848 WCRP [CLIVAR](#) – [OMDP](#) (Ocean Model Development Panel) and [Rifs](#) – [CORDEX](#)
849 (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment).

850 **Why a task force on regional ocean modelling and climate projections?**

- 851 • Identified needs to provide refined regional information (physics, biogeochemistry,
852 sea-ice) on the past, present and future marine and coastal environments, aligned
853 with the scales relevant for society's decision context and to support ocean climate
854 services and climate adaptation measures
- 855 • Most coupled global climate models will not be able to run at high-resolution (i.e.,
856 1/10 of degree in the ocean) in the next decade, leaving a clear gap for dynamical
857 downscaling approaches (e.g., ocean regional climate models, coupled regional
858 climate models) to fill
- 859 • Need to improve regional ocean representation in CORDEX as oceanic areas and
860 ocean models are currently under-represented
- 861 • International coordination of regional ocean modelling and climate projections is
862 lacking
863

864 **Task Force Mission:**

865 The task force will develop a strategic plan for a longer-term WCRP initiative which will aim to:

- 866 • Coordinate regional ocean climate projections (physics, biogeochemistry, sea-ice)
867 worldwide by developing coordinated simulation protocols and by delivering
868 standardized datasets
- 869 • Advance the science of regional ocean climate modelling and projections, including
870 through multi-model assessments, identification of robust biases and underlying
871 processes
- 872 • Engage a large community of regional ocean modelers and model users to provide a
873 forum for sharing knowledge and experience across domains
- 874 • Serve the climate impact and adaptation needs by engaging with relevant
875 users/stakeholders and by providing data and expertise to ocean climate services
- 876 • Contribute to expert assessment reports (e.g., IPCC-AR7, national or regional
877 assessment reports)

878

879 **Task force structure:**

880 **Coordinators:**

- 881 • [Samuel Somot](#), CNRM, Météo-France, France, member of the Med-CORDEX
882 steering committee.
- 883 • [Angélique Melet](#), Mercator Ocean, France, member of CLIVAR OMDP, coordinator of
884 the EC Horizon SEACLIM project (European SEAs CLIMate impact prediction
885 through regional models, 2025-2028). Regional ocean climate projections for the
886 northeastern Atlantic.
887

888 **Members:**

- 889 • [Marine Herrmann](#), LEGOS, France and USTH, Hanoi, Vietnam/Chulalongkorn
890 University, Bangkok, Thailand. Link to CORDEX South-East Asia.
- 891 • [Sheila Estrada](#), CICESE, Mexico. Regional modelling for the Gulf of Mexico. Link to
892 CORDEX Central America.
- 893 • [Markus Meier](#), Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research Warnemünde (IOW),
894 Germany. Chair of the Baltic Earth Science Steering Group. Regional climate
895 projections, marine ecosystems, climate information.
- 896 • [Andrew Orr](#), BAS, UK. Polar regions. Link to Polar-CORDEX.
- 897 • [Marcus Thatcher](#), CSIRO, Australia. CORDEX Science Advisory Team member.
- 898 • [Dorotea Iovino](#), CMCC Foundation, Italy. Co-chair of CLIVAR OMDP. Link to CLIVAR
899 NORP and SORP. Polar Oceans.
- 900 • [Shogo Urakawa](#), Meteorological Research Institute/Japan Meteorological Agency,
901 Japan. Member of CLIVAR OMDP.
- 902 • [Jason Holt](#), NOC, UK. Regional ocean projections, incl. BGC, European NW Shelf.
903 UN Decade FLAME project.
- 904 • [Xuebin Zhang](#), CSIRO, Australia. Regional ocean climate projections, sea-level rise.
905 Former member of CLIVAR Pacific Regional Panel.
- 906 • [E Drenkard](#), GFDL, USA. Regional climate projections, marine ecosystems.
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908 **TF timeline:**

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913 **Annex 2. Inventory of existing regional ocean climate projections**

914 In this table, we summarize a subset of the information received via the ocean climate
915 projections inventory survey. We include the name of the model configuration, the ocean region
916 where the model is focused, the approximate geographic extent, and the horizontal resolution.
917 We also indicate if the model calculates ocean physics, ocean biogeochemistry (BGC), and
918 sea ice. Forcing conditions are characterized as either one-way or coupled with the
919 atmosphere, and we list both the earth system models (ESMs) and/or general circulation
920 models (GCM) and the future scenarios that are downscaled. Lastly, we include linked
921 publications pertaining to the simulations.

Appendix Table 1	Regional Focus Ocean Basin/Regional Sea	Approximate Geographic Extent	Horizontal Resolution	Ocean Model Components			Atmospheric Forcing Coupled vs. One-Way	ESMs/GCMS Downscaled	Future Scenarios	References
				Physics	BGC	Sea Ice				
Model Name										
IBI-CCSv2	Atlantic Ocean North Sea western Mediterranean Sea	26°N-64.2°N x 20°W-17°E	1/12° (6-7 km)	x			One-Way	CNRM-CM6-1-HR CNRM-CM6-1 EC-Earth3 MPI-ESM1-2-HR	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5 5-8.5	Iraozqui Apecechea et al., 2025
GAMAR	Atlantic Ocean Bay of Biscay / English Channel	43°N-51°N x 8°W-2°E	1km	x	x		One-Way	CNRM-RCSM6	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Martinez Almogyna et al., 2025
ROMS-NWP20	Pacific Ocean	15°N-52°N x 115°-164° E	1/20°	x			One-Way	4 from CMIP5 5 from CMIP6	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5, 3-7.0, 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 2.6, 4.5, 6.0, 8.5	Kim et al., 2021 Kim et al., 2025
AMM7	Atlantic Ocean	40°N-65°N x 40°E-65°E	~7km	x	x		One-Way	HadGEM2-ES IPSL-CM5A-MR GFDL-ESM2G	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Galli et al., 2024
OGSTM-BFM	Mediterranean Sea	30°N-45°N x 10°W-38°E	1/16°	x	x		One-Way	CMCC-CM	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Reale et al., 2022
HBM	North Sea and Baltic Sea	48.525°N-65.875°N x 4.125°W-30.292°E	1-25km	x		x	One-Way	DMI-HIRHAM (downscaled from EC-EARTH)	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Šuš et al., 2022 Šuš et al., 2024
SHYFEM	Southeastern Baltic Sea Curonian Lagoon	54.34°N-56.5°N x 19.02°E-21.11°E	0.4-10km	x			One-Way	EC-Earth IPSL-CM 5A-MR HadGEM2-ES MPI-ESM-LR	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Idzelyté et al., 2023 Čerkašova et al., 2024
GCOAST	North Sea Baltic Sea	40.1°N-65.9°N x 19.9°W-30.2°E	3.7km	x	x	x	Coupled	MPI-ESM1-2HR	CMIP6 SSPs 3-7.0	
IBI-CCS	Atlantic Ocean North Sea western Mediterranean Sea	26°N-64.2°N x 20°W-14°E	1/12° (6-7 km)	x			One-Way	CNRM-CM6-1-HR	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 5-8.5	Chaigneau et al., 2022
can11	Atlantic Ocean	8°N-35°N x 30°W-10°W	10km	x			One-Way	ORCA1-PISCES (CMIP ensemble)	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	
CROCO-Pacific	Pacific Ocean	12°N-40°S x 85°W-68°W	1/12° and 1/36°	x	x		One-Way	CESM-LENS	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	
CROCO-Indian	Indian Ocean	5°S-30°S x 25°E-55°E	1/12° and 1/36°	x	x		One-Way	CESM-LENS	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	
eReefs GBR4	Coral Sea	28°S-8°S x 142°E-157°E	~4km	x	x		One-Way	FGOALS, CMCC	CMIP6 SSPs 2-4.5	Schlaefter et al., 2025
Delft3D	Atlantic Ocean	22°S-29°S x 49°W-44°W	0.1-1km	x			One-Way	CMIP	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	
NEMO	Pacific Ocean Indian Ocean Maritime Continent	-16.15°S-24.088°N x 79.68°E-160.248°E	8km	x			One-Way	ACCESS-CM2 EC-EARTH3 MIROC6 MPI-ESM1-2-HR NorESM2-MM UKESM1-0-LL	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5, 5-8.5	
DKSS-2013	North Sea Baltic Sea	48°N-66°N x 5°W-30°E	0.9-5.5km	x		x	One-Way	ensemble of CMIP5 GGMs/ESMs	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Berg and Weismann Poulsen, 2012
NEMOMED-Eco3M-MED	Mediterranean Sea	30°N-46°N x 5°E-36°E	1/8° and 1/12°	x			Coupled	CNRM-CM5	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Pagès et al., 2020
Projections for the Arabian Sea	Arabian Sea	3°S-30.5°N x 32°E-77°E	4km	x			One-Way	BCC-CSM2-MR CESM2 CNRM-ESM2-1 EC-Earth3-Veg HadGEM3-GC31-MM IPSL-CM6A-LR MPI-ESM1-2-HR MRI-ESM2-0	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5, 3-7.0, 5-8.5	
MetROMS-UHel-v1.0	Southern Ocean	90°S-30°S x 0°E-360°E	1/4°	x	x	x	One-Way	MPI-ESM1-2-LR	CMIP6 SSPs 3-7.0	Ajaja et al., 2025
MITgcm-PAS	Southern Ocean	76°S-62°S x 140°W-80°W	1/10°	x		x	One-Way	CESM1 ensembles	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5 stabilisation scenarios 1.5°C and 2°C	Naughten et al., 2023

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ROHO800 ROMS-NERSEM	NE North Sea and adjacent western Norwegian fjords	58.3°N-61.2°N x 2.8°E-7.2°E	0.8km	x	x		One-Way	NorESM2	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	
CBEFS	Chesapeake Bay	36.5°N-39.75°N x 77.5°W-75°W	80-600m	x	x		One-Way	ensemble of CMIP5; ACCESS-CM2 MPI-ESM1-2-HR MRI-ESM2-0	CMIP6 SSPs 2-4.5, 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Bian et al., 2024 Hinson et al., 2023 Hinson et al., 2024 Czajka et al., 2025
Totten	Southern Ocean	70°S-60°S x 90°E-150°E	4-5km	x		x	One-Way	ECCO	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 5-8.5	Pelle et al., 2021
MM7-HadGEM3-GC3.05-PPE	Northwest European Shelf	40°4'N-65° N x 19°W-13°E	7km	x			One-Way	UKCP18	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Tinker et al., 2020 Tinker et al., 2024
CCRS-NEMO-SEAv1.0	Pacific Ocean, Indian Ocean Bay of Bengal, South China Sea Philippine Sea	20°S-20°N x 90°E-120°E	1/12°	x			One-Way	ensemble of CMIP GCMs	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5, 5-8.5	
FORP-NP10	Pacific Ocean	15°S-63°N x 99°E-75°W	1/11°-1/10°	x	x	x	One-Way	MIROC5 MRI-CGCM3 GFDL-ESM2M IPSL-CM5A-MR	CMIP5 RCPs 2.6, 8.5	Nishikawa et al., 2021 Nishikawa et al., 2024
FORP-JPN02	seas around Japan	20°N-52°N x 117°E-160°E	1/50°-1/33°	x		x	One-Way	MIROC5 MRI-CGCM3	CMIP5 RCPs 2.6, 8.5	Nishikawa et al., 2021
AUSROD-MITgcm	Pacific Ocean Indian Ocean	55°S-5°S x 100°E-180°E	1/12°	x			One-Way	8 CMIP6 GCMs 17 CMIP5 GCMs	CMIP6 SSPs 2-4.5, 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	
AUSROD-ROMS	Pacific Ocean Indian Ocean	50°S-5°S x 100°E-180°E	1/12°	x			One-Way	8 CMIP6 GCMs	CMIP6 SSPs 2-4.5, 5-8.5	
CCAM coupled UQ-Qld Gov version	Global	global (highly resolved around Australia)	~0.1°	x		x	Coupled	ACCESS-ESM1.5 ACCESS-CM2 CNRM-CM6-1-HR NorESM2-MM	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5 3-7.0	Chapman et al., 2023 Chapman et al., 2024

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CNRM-RCSM4	Mediterranean Sea	30°N-46°N x 11°W to 37°E	1/12°	x			Coupled	CNRM-CM5.1	CMIP5 RCPs 2.6, 4.5, 8.5	Tinker et al., 2024 Soto-Navarro et al., 2020
CNRM-RCSM6	Mediterranean Sea	30°N-46°N x 11°W to 37°E	1/12°	x			Coupled	CNRM-ESM2-1	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	Parras-Berrocal et al., 2024
Talesm downscaling	Pacific Ocean	5°N-40°N x 95°E-160°E	9km	x			One-Way	TaiESM	CMIP6 SSPs 2-4.5, 5-8.5	
ROMS CCS/ROMS WC12	Pacific Ocean California Current System	30°N-48°N x 136°W -115°W	10km	x	x		One-Way	GFDL-ESM2M HadGEM2-ES IPSL-CM5A-MR	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	Pozo Buil et al., 2021 Pozo Buil et al., 2023
East Asian Marginal Seas Downscaling	Pacific Ocean	2°N-41°N x 99°E-140°E	1/12°	x			One-Way	8 CMIP Models and their ensembles	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	
Tropical Pacific basin	Pacific Ocean	30°S-30°N x 80°E-290°E	1-8km	x			Both	CMIP ensemble	CMIP6 SSPs 3-7.0	
AMM7-RECICLE	NW European Shelf	40°N-63°N x 20°W-12°E	7km	x	x		One-Way	GFDL-ESM2G GFDL-ESM2M HadGEM2-CC HadGEM2-ES IPSL-CM5A-LR IPSL-CM5A-MR IPSL-CM5B-LR BCC-CSM1-1-m CanESM2 CNRM-CM5 MIROC-ESM	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Holt et al., 2022 Galli et al., 2024
ROM	Atlantic Ocean Mediterranean Indian Ocean Arctic Ocean Pacific Ocean	10°S-60°N x 90°W-45°E	7-25km	x		x	Coupled	AWICM	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	
SEAsia (South East Asia)	Indian Ocean Pacific Ocean	20°S-25°N x 75°E-135°E	1/12°	x	x		One-Way	HadGEM2	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Jardine et al., 2025
SG1000-NWP-RCP85	Indian Ocean	35.75°S-32.25°S x 135.25°E-138.25°E	1km	x			One-Way	ESM2M	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	
NTALT025	Atlantic Ocean	5°S-35°N x 100°W-20°E	1/4°	x			Coupled	CMIP ensemble	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Gevaudan et al., 2021

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NEP36-CanOE	Pacific Ocean	44.332672°N- 59.633045°N x 120.540855°W-142.28317°W	1/36°	x	x		One-Way	CanESM2 CanRCM4	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Holdsworth et al., 2021
SalishSeaCast	Salish Sea	47°N-51°N x 234°E-238°E	~0.5km	x	x		One-Way	CanESM2	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	
CCS-downscaled-IPSL	Pacific Ocean	28°N-50°N x 130°W-115°W	12km, 4km, 1km	x	x		One-Way	CMIP6	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	
CANOPA-GSBM	Atlantic Ocean	38.5°N-52°N x 72°W-55°W	1/12°	x	x	x	One-Way	MPI-ESM-LR HadGEM2-ES CanESM2	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Mei et al., 2024 Lavioie et al., 2020
Nemo-NAA10km	Atlantic Ocean Arctic Ocean	35°N-90°N x 180°W-180°E (omitting Sea of Okhotsk, Mediterranean Sea)	10km	x		x	One-Way	NorESM EC-Earth	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 3-7.0, 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 2.6, 4.5, 8.5	Sandje et al., 2020 Nielsen et al., 2023
NAA-CanOE-CSIB /UVIC model/IOS model	Arctic Ocean	65°N-90°N x 0°-360°E	11-15km	x	x	x	One-Way	CanRCM CanESM ECEarth	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Hayashida et al., 2020 Mortenson et al., 2020 Haddon et al., 2024 Haddon et al., 2025
BASS2	Pacific Ocean	41.5°S-36.5°S x 140°E-152°E	2km	x	x		One-Way	CMIPHighRes CMCC-CM2-VHR4	CMIP6 SSPs 2-4.5	
RAISE	Southern Ocean	64°S-90°S x 155°E-89°W	2.5km	x		x	One-Way	Ensemble mean of CMIP6 models	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	Zhang et al., 2025
TOPAZ	Arctic Ocean Atlantic Ocean	45°N-90°N x -180°-180°	17km	x	x	x	One-Way	NorESM2-MM	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	
NEMO-MED12-PISCES	Mediterranean Sea	30°N-48°N x 10.5°W-43E°	1/12°	x	x		Coupled	LMdz or Meteo france	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 5-8.5	Richon et al., 2019
Norkyst (Norwegian coastal model)	The Norwegian Coast	2°S-40°N x 55°N-75°N	0.8km	x			One-Way	NorESM	CMIP6 SSPs 3-7.0	
BSEM	Black Sea	40.9°N-46.5667°N x 27.7667°E-41.7333°E	1/30°	x	x		One-Way	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5	Macias Moy et al., 2022 Miladinova et al., 2024
EBU-POM	Mediterranean Sea	30°N-48°N x 6°W-37E° (omitting Black Sea)	30km	x			Coupled		CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	

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Salish Sea Model	Pacific Ocean Salish Sea	44°N-52°N x 131°W-122°W	100m-3km	x	x		One-Way	CMIP	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	
KRCM (KIOST Regional Climate Model)	Pacific Ocean	22°N-54°N x 117°E-150°E	1/20°	x	x		Coupled	CMIP6	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Jung et al., 2015
AMM7 - NEMO Shelf Climate	Atlantic Ocean	13°S-19N x 40°E-65°E	7km	x			One-Way	HadGEM3 PPE	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	Tinker et al., 2018 Tinker et al., 2024
POLCOMS Minerva Projections	Atlantic Ocean	43°N-63°N x 18°W-13°E	7km	x			One-Way	HadCM3 Perturbed Parameter Ensemble	SRES A1B	Tinker et al., 2016 Tinker et al., 2020
RCO-SCOBI	Baltic Sea	54°N-66°N x 9°E-30°E	3.7km	x	x	x	One-Way	MPI-ESM-LR EC-Earth IPSL-CM5A-MR HadGEM2-ES	CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Saraiva et al., 2019 Meier et al., 2021 Meier et al., 2022
ROM-Global	Global	45°S-60°N x 30°W-40°E	12km	x		x	Coupled	AWICM 1	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Tamoffo et al., 2024
ROM-Atlantic	Atlantic Mediterranean Sea	40°S-45°N x 90°W-140°E	5-50km	x	x	x	Coupled	AWI-CM	CMIP6 SSPs 3-7.0, 5-8.5	
RCA4-NEMO	North Sea - Baltic Sea	46°N-68°N x 4°W-30°E	~3.7km	x		x	Coupled	CMIP5 ensemble	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 2.6, 4.5	Dieterich et al., 2019 Gröger et al., 2019 Gröger et al., 2015
(COSMO-CLM, NEMO-MED, TRIP, OASIS) - EC-Earth3-Veg	Mediterranean Sea	25.63N-52.34N x 6.04W-50.85E	0.083°	x			Coupled	EC-EARTH3-Veg	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	
(COSMO-CLM, NEMO-MED, TRIP, OASIS) - EC-Earth	Mediterranean Sea	25.63N-52.34N x 6.04W-50.85E	0.083°	x			Coupled	EC-EARTH	CMIP5 RCPs 8.5	
FESOM-1.4, FESOM-PISM	Southern Ocean	global (highly resolved Southern Ocean)	2-30km	x		x	One-Way			

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North Atlantic Ocean Downscaling System	Atlantic Ocean	7°N-66°N x 260°E-360°E	1/12° - 1/4°	x		x	One-Way	HadCM3	SRES-A1B	Han et al., 2025
ROMS-BEC CCS 12 km	Pacific Ocean	15°N-60°N x 215°W-245°W	12km	x	x		One-Way	GFDL-ESM2M HadGEM2-ES IPSL-CM5A-LR MPI-ESM-LR CESM1(BGC) Ensemble mean of above	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 4.5, 8.5	Howard et al., 2020 Siedlecki et al., 2021
ROMS Bering10K	Pacific Ocean	50°N-66°N x 170°E-150°W	10km	x	x	x	One-Way	MIROC, CESM, GFDL,	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5, 5-8.5 CMIP5 RCPs 2.6, 4.5, 8.5	
ROMS-NEP	Pacific Ocean	54°N-61°N x 160°W-132°W	10km	x			One-Way	GFDL-ESM4	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5, 5-8.5	Bovelli et al., 2025
NWA-ROMs	Pacific Ocean Atlantic Ocean	8.8°N-53.8°N x 106.3°W-49.2°W	7km	x	x		One-Way	GFDL-ESM4	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	Siedlecki et al., in review
INCOIS-FRONTIER	Indian Ocean	30°S-30°N x 30°E-120°E	1/12°	x	x		One-Way	GFDL-ESM4 UKESM1-0-LL CNRM-ESM2-1	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	Ghoshal et al., 2025 Chakraborty et al., 2024
Baja California Experiment	Pacific Ocean	23°N-35°N x 237°E-250°E	8km	x	x		One-Way	GFDL-CM3	CMIP5 RCPs 6.0, 8.5	Arellano and Rivas, 2019
WRF-ROMS	Atlantic Ocean	5°N-50°N x 140°W-50°W	6km	x			Coupled	CMIP6 models	CMIP6 SSPs 5-8.5	Tian et al. (in review)
FESOM-REcoM-AntarcticShelf	Global with enhanced resolution in the Southern Ocean and Antarctic continental shelf	global (highly resolved over Antarctica)	2-100km	x	x	x	One-Way	AWI CM	CMIP6 SSPs 1-2.6, 2-4.5, 3-7.0, 5-8.5	Nissen et al., 2022 Nissen et al., 2023 Nissen et al., 2024a Nissen et al., 2024b Nissen et al., 2025
Peru6	Pacific Ocean	40°S-15°S x 100°W-70°W	1/6°	x			One-Way	IPSL-CM4	CMIP4 Scenarios 2xCO2, 4xCO2	

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937 **Annex 3. CMIP7 Data Request for Regional Ocean Climate Projections**

938 Submitted in fall 2024 to the CMIP7 Data Request - CORDEX OPPORTUNITY.

939 **Description of the CORDEX Opportunity:** High-resolution climate simulations performed
940 with RCMs are increasingly used to feed climate services on a wealth of applications. CORDEX
941 model output is an authoritative source of downscaled data due to the controlled and
942 coordinated experimental setup. CORDEX dynamical downscaling activity (and other RCMs)
943 require high-frequency lateral boundary conditions from GCMs for the historical and scenario
944 periods.

945 **Justification of Resources:** Downscaling is a key step in filling the gap between CMIP7 global
946 climate model experiments and the activity of the communities dealing with vulnerability,
947 impacts and adaptation studies.

948

949 **Dynamical Downscaling Ocean (CORDEX) core**

950 **Justification:** There is an emerging need for regional downscaling of global climate models
951 for the ocean (physics, biogeochemistry, sea ice) to provide refined and more regional-to-local
952 information on marine environment past and projections changes, to support ocean climate
953 services and for climate adaptation. A set of variables are needed to force regional ocean
954 models at their lateral boundaries, and at the air-sea interface for forced models.

955

Dynamical_downscaling_ocean_core (11 variables)		
Variables	MIP Variables	CF Standard Name
Omon.thetao	thetao	sea_water_potential_temperature
Omon.so	so	sea_water_salinity
Omon.uo	uo	sea_water_x_velocity
Omon.vo	vo	sea_water_y_velocity

Omon.zos	zos	sea_surface_height_above_geoid
Omon.tos	tos	sea_surface_temperature
Omon.sos	sos	sea_surface_salinity
Omon.zostoga	zostoga	global_average_thermosteric_sea_level_change
Omon.friver	friver	water_flux_into_sea_water_from_rivers
Omon.ficeberg	ficeberg	water_flux_into_sea_water_from_icebergs
Omon.masscello	masscello	sea_water_mass_per_unit_area

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957

958 **Dynamical Downscaling Ocean air/sea forcing (CLIVAR/CORDEX)**

959 **Justification:** Dynamical downscaling of the ocean requires hourly forcing fields at the air sea
960 interface for specific variables.

961

962 The following variables should also be stored hourly (not available hourly in CMIP6): 3hr.prsn,
963 3hr.tauuo, 3hr.tauvo

964

Dynamical_downscaling_ocean_air_sea_forcing (11 variables)		
Variables	MIP Variables	CF Standard Name
E1hr.tas	tas	air_temperature
E1hr.huss	huss	specific_humidity
E1hr.uas	uas	eastward_wind
E1hr.vas	vas	northward_wind
E1hr.rsds	rsds	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air
E1hr.rlds	rlds	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air
E1hr.psl	psl	air_pressure_at_mean_sea_level
E1hr.pr	pr	precipitation_flux

3hr.prsn	prsn	snowfall_flux
3hr.tauuo	tauuo	downward_x_stress_at_sea_water_surface
3hr.tauvo	tauvo	downward_y_stress_at_sea_water_surface

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966 **Dynamical Downscaling Ocean biogeochemistry forcing (CLIVAR/CORDEX)**

967 **Justification:** Dynamical downscaling of the ocean biogeochemistry requires monthly 3D-
968 global forcing fields for specific variables.

969 The following variables are still missing:

- 970 • Dissolved inorganic N from rivers
- 971 • Dissolved inorganic P from rivers
- 972 • Dissolved inorganic Si from rivers

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Dynamical_downscaling_ocean_biogeochemistry_forcing (26 variables)		
Variables	MIP Variables	CF Standard Name
Omon.phyc	phyc	mole_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.phydiat	phydiat	mole_concentration_of_diatoms_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.phydiaz	phydiaz	mole_concentration_of_diazotrophic_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.phycalc	phycalc	mole_concentration_of_calcareous_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.phypico	phypico	mole_concentration_of_picophytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.phymisc	phymisc	mole_concentration_of_miscellaneous_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water

Omon.zooc	zooc	mole_concentration_of_zooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.zmicro	zmicro	mole_concentration_of_microzooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.zmeso	zmeso	mole_concentration_of_mesozooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.zmisc	zmisc	mole_concentration_of_miscellaneous_zooplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.chl	chl	mass_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water
Omon.chldiat	chldiat	mass_concentration_of_diatoms_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water
Omon.chldiaz	chldiaz	mass_concentration_of_diazotrophic_phytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water
Omon.chlpico	chlpico	mass_concentration_of_picophytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water
Omon.chlmisc	chlmisc	mass_concentration_of_miscellaneous_phytoplankton_expressed_as_chlorophyll_in_sea_water
Omon.no3	no3	mole_concentration_of_nitrate_in_sea_water
Omon.po4	po4	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_phosphorus_in_sea_water
Omon.si	si	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_silicon_in_sea_water
Omon.o2	o2	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_molecular_oxygen_in_sea_water

Omon.dissic	dissic	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_inorganic_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.talk	talk	sea_water_alkalinity_expressed_as_mole_equivalent
Omon.dissoc	dissoc	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_organic_carbon_in_sea_water
Omon.dfe	dfe	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_iron_in_sea_water
Omon.icfriver	icfriver	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_inorganic_carbon_due_to_runoff_and_sediment_dissolution
Omon.ocfriver	ocfriver	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_organic_carbon_due_to_runoff_and_sediment_dissolution
Omon.phycos	phycos	mole_concentration_of_phytoplankton_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water

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975

976 **Dynamical Downscaling Ocean air-sea biogeochemistry forcing (CLIVAR/CORDEX)**

977 **Justification:** Dynamical downscaling of the ocean air-sea biogeochemistry requires daily 3D-
978 global forcing fields for specific variables.

Dynamical_downscaling_ocean_air_sea_biogeochemistry_forcing		
(7 variables)		
Variables	MIP Variables	CF Standard Name
AERmon.drydust	drydust	minus_tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dust_dry_aerosol_particles_due_to_dry_deposition
AERmon.drynoy	drynoy	minus_tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_noy_expressed_as_nitrogen_due_to_dry_deposition
AERmon.wetdust	wetdust	minus_tendency_of_atmosphere_mass_content_of_dust_dry_aerosol_particles_due_to_wet_deposition

AERmon.wetnoy	wetnoy	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_elemental_nitrogen_due_to_deposition_and_fixation_and_runoff
Omon.spcO2	spco2	surface_partial_pressure_of_carbon_dioxide_in_sea_water
Omon.fsfe	fsfe	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_iron_due_to_deposition_and_runoff_and_sediment_dissolution
Omon.fsn	fsn	tendency_of_ocean_mole_content_of_elemental_nitrogen_due_to_deposition_and_fixation_and_runoff

979

980 **Annex 4. Proposed revision of ocean reference regions**

Index	Acronym	Name	Type	Continent / Ocean
1	OAG	Agulhas-Current	Coastal	Africa
2	OCAN	Canary-Current	Coastal	Africa
3	OSCC	Somali-Coastal-Current	Coastal	Africa
4	OGC	Guinea-Current	Coastal	Africa
5	OBEC	Benguela-Current	Coastal	Africa
6	ORES	Red-Sea	Regional-Sea	Africa
7	OARS	Arabian-Sea	Regional-Sea	Asia
8	OBB	Bay-of-Bengal	Regional-Sea	Asia
9	OSC	Sulu-Celebes-Seas	Regional-Sea	Asia
10	OIDS	Indonesian-Sea	Regional-Sea	Asia
11	OKOC	Kuroshio-Oyashio-Currents	Coastal	Asia
12	OOKS	Okhotsk.Sea	Regional-Sea	Asia
13	OSCT	South-China-Sea&Gulf-of-Thailand	Regional-Sea	Asia
14	OSJ	Sea-of-Japan	Regional-Sea	Asia
15	OYEC	Yellow&East-China-Seas	Regional-Sea	Asia
16	OBAL	Baltic-Sea	Regional-Sea	Europe
17	OBLK	Black-Sea	Regional-Sea	Europe
18	OCP	Caspian-Sea	Regional-Sea	Europe
19	OENW	European.North-West-Shelf	Regional-Sea	Europe
20	OIB	Iberia.Bay-of-Biscay	Regional-Sea	Europe

21	OMED	Mediterranean-Sea	Regional-Sea	Europe-Africa
22	OENA	E.North-America	Coastal	North-America
23	OGA	Gulf-of-Alaska	Coastal	North-America
24	OHB	Hudson-Bay-Complex	Regional-Sea	North-America
25	OCG	California-Current-Gulf	Coastal	Central-America
26	OPCA	Pacific.Central-America	Coastal	Central-America
27	OCAR	Caribbean-Sea	Regional-Sea	Central-America
28	OGM	Gulf.of.Mexico	Regional-Sea	Central-America
29	OBNE	N.E.Brazil-Shelf	Coastal	South-America
30	OBS	S.Brazil-Shelf	Coastal	South-America
30	OPTS	Patagonian-Shelf	Coastal	South-America
31	OHC	Humboldt-Current	Coastal	South-America
32	OAUW	W.Australian-Shelf	Coastal	Oceania
33	OAUE	E.Australian-Shelf	Coastal	Oceania
34	OAUN	N.Australian-Shelf	Coastal	Oceania
35	OAUS	S.Australian-Shelf	Coastal	Oceania
36	OTAS	Tasman-Sea	Ocean	Oceania
37	ONZ	New-Zealand-Shelf	Coastal	Oceania
38	OAB	Admundsen&Bellingshausen-Seas	Regional-Sea	S.Polar
39	ORO	Ross-Sea	Regional-Sea	S.Polar
40	OWE	Weddell-Sea	Regional-Sea	S.Polar
41	OEAN	E.Antarctica.Ocean	Coastal	S.Polar
42	ONG	Norwegian&Greenland-Seas	Regional-Sea	N.Polar

43	OBA	Barents-Sea	Regional-Sea	N.Polar
44	OKA	Kara-Sea	Regional-Sea	N.Polar
45	OLP	Laptev-Sea	Regional-Sea	N.Polar
46	OES	E.Siberian-Sea	Regional-Sea	N.Polar
47	OCH	Chuckchi-Sea	Regional-Sea	N.Polar
48	OBF	Beaufort-Sea	Regional-Sea	N.Polar
49	OGR	N.W.Greenland	Regional-Sea	N.Polar
50	OAEQ	Equatorial.Atlantic-Ocean	Ocean	Atlantic
51	OANE	E.North-Atlantic-Ocean	Ocean	Atlantic
52	OANS	S.North-Atlantic-Ocean	Ocean	Atlantic
53	OASN	N.South-Atlantic-Ocean	Ocean	Atlantic
54	OASS	S.South-Atlantic-Ocean	Ocean	Atlantic
55	OANWC	Western&Central.North-Atlantic-Ocean	Ocean	Atlantic
56	OARC	Central-Arctic-Ocean	Ocean	Arctic
57	OIEQ	Equatorial.Indian-Ocean	Ocean	Indian
58	OIS	S.Indian-Ocean	Ocean	Indian
59	OPEQW	W.Equatorial.Pacific-Ocean	Ocean	Pacific
60	OPEQE	E.Equatorial.Pacific-Ocean	Ocean	Pacific
61	OPNN	N.North-Pacific-Ocean	Ocean	Pacific
62	OPNS	S.North-Pacific-Ocean	Ocean	Pacific
63	OPS	S.Pacific-Ocean	Ocean	Pacific
64	OBE	Bering-Sea	Regional-Sea	Pacific

65	OSO	Southern-Ocean	Ocean	Southern
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